

8- Theory Primordial Coupling Constants Equation and the Rise of the Arrow of Time

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Abstract:

This paper will analyze the coupling constant equation in the context of the arrow of time. By analyzing the equation it is vivid that it must be one sided. The analysis done on the electromagnetism coupling constant. Reader should be familiar with the 8-theory Framework and in particular with the primordial function prediction coupling constant magnitudes, and all of the representations of the equation. In here, mainly analysis on the first and second representation, i.e. net variations of a Lorentz manifold and spin using the prime critical line.

Introduction

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{i=1}^{i=R} N(V)_i + (3) \right) + N(V)_i = 9:30:128:850:9254 \dots \quad (1)$$

$$N(V)_i = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0$$

$$N(V)_i \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N(V)_i = P_{max} \text{ in Range } [0, \mathbb{R}]$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (2)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) \dots \quad (3)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Suppose a boson was emitted from a fermion due to net variation of a certain magnitude. If the arrow of time is two sided and reversible, there must be a way to bring the photon back to the electron. However, the physics of the 20-th Century forbids us from doing that, as we don't even know where the photon is.

Momentum and position are conjugate variables in quantum field theory. So once a boson is propagated into the metric, there is no possible way to bring it where it was. An additional argument is that all bosons are indistinguishable, so even if it was possible to trace and revert the photon, in a system with more than one Photon, its again beyond reach.

The reason we emphasize those arguments as to the context of the arrow of time. At first, at a certain point after the singularity, there were only elements of the first Element in the coupling series on the expended manifold:

$$8 + (1)$$

If the expended manifold experience multiple net variations of the first element than it is possible to cluster those:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{n=\infty} C(n) = 8 + (1) \quad (5)$$

We can cluster into groups of three and get:

$$(8 * 3) + (1) * 3 = 24 + (3) \quad (6)$$

The invariant three, in 8-theory framework is, as you already know, is the destabilizing factor yielding a net variation so overall:

$$24 + (3) \rightarrow [24 + (3)] + 3 \quad (7)$$

Therefore, we can derive the intimate relation between the coupling constant series and the direction of time. The following procedure can be done on any additional element in the series. **In the 8-theory what is time?**

Time is the result of net variations being clustered to different magnitudes. The succession of bosons with decreasing magnitude converging to zero is the direction of the arrow. The fact that each element is different than is preceding is the physical manifestation of the arrow of time. This equation encompass all the interactions according to magnitude, and so as those are different, the difference is the factor that gives rise to the arrow. If all elements in the series were identical there could not be a rise to the arrow.

Using that coupling constant equation, we can reason for the chronology of events from the moment of singularity to the present moment. We can reason for electrons propagation only after protons were created. We can reason gravitational interactions only after electric interactions and we possibly can reason also, how galaxies were formed.

Notice that the fourth element in the series is only 6.65 weaker than the electric. That is immensely stronger than the gravitational interaction and using that element as a building block for clustering after electric interactions and it is possible to explain how relatively fast galaxies formed in a short window of time, from the manifold being too hot to being too cold.

References

[1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)